

THE IMPORTANCE OF GUIDES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Abstract

This article explores the importance of guides in the development of the tourism industry. The guide should ensure that in the course of the excursion, the excavators will be able to think in harmony, analyze, express sympathy, unite in their interests and become a team. The guide should focus on not only educational, but also educational aspects of the excursion service.

Key words. Guide, excursion, tourism, person, tradition, culture.

Introduction

Today, great importance is attached to the rapid development of the tourism sector in our country, and in the medium term, the implementation of the program for the development of domestic tourism "travel through the regions of the Republic" was established. The implementation of these tasks requires further development of Tourism and excursion services in Uzbekistan. In the tourism sector, excursion service is one of the main services. Any tourist who visits first of all wants to get acquainted with the history, culture, social life, natural resources of the country, watch. The excursion service, with its exhibitionism, content, sensuality, influences the formation of the spiritual worldview of the excavators.

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The tasks facing the excursion service can be manifested as follows;

Sees;

Hears;

Feels;

Will acquire the skill.

GID's work was not regarded as a profession until the recent past, when it was an interesting occupation for an amateur group, except for. The work of the Gid was carried out by specialists from different fields without separation from their main activities (educators, museum scientists, scientific staff of the Institute, etc.k). Only a few excursion institutions and separate museums have only guides in the state. But it was then that this activity began to acquire professional characteristics. The change in the function of the excursion service, its transformation from a form of recreation to an organizational form of cultural and educational work in labor communities, the transformation into a network serving the population, led to an increase in the role of a new specialty, that is, gid. Article 3 of the law "on tourism" of the Republic of Uzbekistan includes the concepts of head of tourist group (turlider) and gid (tour leader). According to him, the definitions are included – the head of the tourist group – a person who is a representative of the subjects of tourist activity and acts on his behalf, ensuring the fulfillment of the terms of the tourist service contract“, "Gid (ekaskursuya leader) –an individual who provides excursion - information, organizational services and

qualified assistance to the participants of the tour." Each guide is required to know not only the knowledge of their specialty, but also the basics of pedagogy and psychology. It is necessary that the guide correctly analyzes his work, gives an objective assessment of the excursion service he conducted, is principled and self-demanding. GID's communication with excavators, his recommendations, instructions have an educational effect. The information studied enriches their consciousness spiritually and aesthetically. Thus, the excursion service is part of the pedagogical process, provides education, upbringing to a person, forms his worldview. As with all pedagogical processes, the excursion service is attended by two sides: the teacher-guide and the learner-excavator. The guide provides knowledge on a specific topic, while the excavants accept it. The mutual action of these two parties is the basis of the pedagogical process. In interaction with excavants, gid employs methods of pedagogical influence. Pedagogical skill, pedagogical art form the component of the Gid professional qualification. GID's pedagogical skills include: - sufficient knowledge of the specialty; -the ability to analyze, to think figuratively;- to understand the spirit of the excavator;- to be able to control the group;- to acquire knowledge and skills from the field of pedagogical technology;- intuition; - respect for the personality of the excavator. The Gid profession requires a clear practical qualification. This skill gives him the opportunity to correctly select, embody and effectively transfer his knowledge to the audience.

The guide should ensure that in the course of the excursion, the excavators will be able to think in harmony, analyze, express sympathy, unite in their interests and become a team. The guide should focus on not only educational, but also educational aspects of the excursion service. He should choose and use excursion information in such a way that qualities such as love for the motherland, respect for other nations, their fertility appear in the excavators. In addition to choosing and giving complete, accurate information about objects to excavators, the guide must also have personal qualities, professional skills. Moral requirements for an individual are the observance of general principles and moral standards, the pursuit of perfection. The formation of an individual as perfect and harmonious in every possible way occurs throughout his life (in a comprehensive school, college, OTM, team, everyday life, in courses preparing guides, in interaction with excavators). The main activity of GID is the preparation and conduct of an excursion service. The preparation of the excursion service is divided into 3 Parts: 1) preparation of Individual Text; 2) remembering the requirements of methodological development; 3) keeping the route in mind. In order for the guide to be able to attract ecuscursants during the excursion, to keep the atmosphere of the group stable, it is necessary to work on it and improve the following 4 types of abilities:

- Constructivism;
- Organization;
- Comunicativity;

-Analysis. The ability to constructivism is expressed in the likes of being able to correctly select and formalize the data of the ecosturation service for ecosurcants, communicate it intelligibly and reliably, and, if necessary, re-see the excursion plan, the procedure for using methodological instructions, and is the basis of the ability to think gid. Organizational skills are reflected in the ability to lead an excursion group, direct their attention to the desired object, perform services in the approved program for tourists and excavators. The ability to communicativeness is manifested in the process of establishing a warm relationship with each other when working with an excursion group, maintaining this

environment during the excursion service, being able to assimilate the nature of the culture of treatment and establishing a proper relationship with the bus driver, exhibition, museum workers, methodological circle leaders, other guides, leaders of the tourist group during the External speech is of communicative importance, the essence of which is directed to the auditory comprehension of other people. "Establishing contact with many listeners of a single speaker is a relatively complex communicative process. GID's story is an example of external speech whose function is to influence the minds and actions of excavators, communicating information about specific objects. Inner speech is the speech of the inner world of a person, a pre-formation of thoughts that will have to be conveyed in the audience. A person maintains a dialogue with his inner voice, thinking about a subject. Thinking with the help of his inner speech, it uses auxiliary tools such as drawings, images, tables. As we talk about the audience listening to public speech, the audience can be complex and extremely complex. Therefore, as the speaker(guide) goes out to the big public, he should definitely prepare seriously, be prepared for any situation, questions. The requirements for the guide should be embodied in the external appearance of the guide:

- compliance with personal hygiene;
- tidy appearance;
- discipline in their actions;
- cultured dress;
- should not smoke during work. In turn, such properties make a warm impression on

the excavators. It should also have personal qualities. For example,

- good physical health;
- mental stability;
- accessibility;
- be disciplined in order;
- be polite;

- must have an artistic ability to be a director and organizer. Because, the guide is not only a representative of the tourfirma, which organizes the trip, but also a person who advertises the potential of his state, gives the Mexicans a new MA'umot and helps them carry out certain actions. The most important thing is that the guide should be able to provide medical care 1 in case of an accident.

Conclusion the development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the training of all personnel and specialists related to this area, the meeting of the visitor in accordance with all standards and providing them with high-quality services, the ability to show the history, culture, traditions of our country accompanied by guides and gain the interest of tourists is one of the important tasks. Hence, the field of guide accompaniment serves as an advertiser of the tourist potential of our country and an attraction for tourists

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